

A STUDY ON CUSTOMER PERCEPTION AND ATTITUDE TOWARDS BRANDED BROADBAND

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Abstract:

Perception is one of the most psychological factors affecting human behavior perception involves selectivity, organizing and interpreting the sensations. The main objective of the study is that to study the awareness of branded broadband services and to study the perception and attitude towards branded broadband. For this purpose a sample of 240 was collected and percentage analysis and chi-square were used as tools to analyse the data and the conclusion is that when taking the overall survey into consideration the respondents are happy and liked the services provided by their service provider which shall be maintained to keep their customers satisfied to achieve greater heights in the years to come.

Key Words: Psychological Factors, Awareness & Broadband

Introduction:

The marketing scenario has changed today with an increasing emphasis on customer delight rather than just customer satisfaction. There is a tendency in marketing to think mostly about what customers care about. That is what benefits customers really want, but there is another important part that should be deeply appreciated by anyone who markets products, and that is customer perceptions, or how customers view (or perceive) the different products on the market. One technique that clearly depicts these customer perceptions is 'snake-plot'. It is a technique that falls under the umbrella terms of 'perceptual mapping'.

Perception / Awareness:

Perception is one of the most psychological factors affecting human behavior perception involves selectivity, organizing and interpreting the sensations. The perception is an individual experiences, a situation it may be recognized that is a unique interpretation of the situation, not necessarily on exact recording of the situation the perception may be defined as the process of selection organization and of sensation to provide the meaningful experience for the individual.

Perception is the process by which physical sensations such as sights, sounds and smells are selected, organized and interpreted. The eventual interpretation of a stimulus allows to be assigned meaning. Marketing stimuli have important sensory qualities. People have different thresholds of perceptions.

Perception is defined as "the process by which an individual selects, organizes and interprets stimulate into a meaningful and coherent picture of the world.

The key word in the definition of perception is individual. One person might perceive a fast – talking sales person as aggressive and insincere, another as intelligent and helpful.

Objectives of the Study:

- ✓ To study the awareness of branded broadband services
- ✓ To study the perception and attitude towards branded broadband.

Research Methodology:

Sample Size: 240

Sampling Procedure:

The sampling method used in the research is probability sampling.

Sources of Data:

Primary Data Collection:

A method of collecting data was through personal interaction by using questionnaire.

Secondary Data Collection:

The secondary data was gathered from the journals, magazines and web sites.

Data Analysis:

The data collected was tabulated, analyzed and interpreted using Simple Percentage Method, and chi-square.

Review of Literature:

Ann Moyal (1989) in her research examined how women who are considered more family oriented than men use and view the telephone. The average house holder makes about one hundred and twenty calls per month. The phone is an extension and intrinsic art of the users other social activities; it is not use as a compensation or a replacement for them.

In Noble (1988) study, it has been observed that talking over the phone is faster than writing. Rutter (1984) further adds that, when talking over the phone, there are often long gaps of silences, because of a lack of visual signals. This brings about the theory of “carelessness”.

Sex Difference in Telephone Use:

“Noble (1987) study, finds significant sex differences in intrinsic telephone use, teenagers are a unique group, and women used the telephone for more intrinsic purposes than instrumental ones. This probably results from the fact that most women are household and therefore the phone is, by & large, their sole connection with the outside world. This view was strongly supported by Noble (1991). This concept was further underlined when Moyal (1989) agreed that it was feminine culture.

Tonnies (1940) study, noted that intrinsic calls from relatives and friends make women feel happy and content. Maddox (1997) suggests that women use the telephone more extensively than men, kumin & Rodin (1982) found that women tend to self – disclose more than men over the telephone. Birren et al (1981) note that women make use of greater verbal abilities over the phon. Rakow (1986) noted that men disliked the telephone & this was the reason for the unequal distribution of phone usage.

Analysis and Interpretation:

		Count	%
Service Provider	BSNL	61	25.42
	Airtel	43	17.92
	Reliance	32	13.33
	Aircel	25	10.42
	Vodaphone	16	6.67
	MTS	38	15.83
	Others (Docomo, Idea, etc.)	25	10.42
	Total	240	100
Monthly Broadband Expenses	Less than Rs.500	63	26.25
	Rs.500 to 1000	132	55
	Rs.1000 to 1500	4	1.67
	Rs.1500 to 2000	27	11.25
	More than Rs.2000	14	5.83
	Total	240	100
Level of Awareness about the Speed provided the broadband service provider	Highly Aware	29	12.08
	Aware	149	62.08
	Not Aware	62	25.83
	Total	240	100
Prime usage of your branded broadband services	Searching for information	184	76.67
	Personal or Business Purposes	224	93.33
	Usage of Services (Bill Payment, etc.)	221	92.08
	Email & instant messaging	222	92.5
	Children learning	129	53.75
	Search engines & purchase products	219	91.25
	Play games & gamble	200	83.33
	Share music file or photos	220	91.67
	Banking, trading stocks, or bill payment	222	92.5
Download movies to view on PC	217	90.42	

Interpretation:

(25.42%) of the respondents have opted BSNL as their service provider for the broadband services, followed by 17.92% of the respondents opted Airtel, 15.83% of the respondents opted MTS, 13.33% of the respondents selected Reliance, 10.42% of the respondents opted Aircel, while another 10.42% of the respondents opted others namely, Docomo, Idea, etc. and the remaining 6.67% of the respondents opted Vodaphone as their service provider for their usage of broadband. (55%) of the respondents incurred expenses between Rs.500 to 1000 per month, whereas 26.25% of the respondents monthly broadband expenses was found to be less than Rs.500, 11.25% of the respondents monthly broadband expenses was from Rs.15000 to 2000, 5.83% of the respondents incurred expenses more than Rs.2000 per month and the remaining 1.67% of the respondents incurred between Rs.1000 and 15000. (62.08%) of the respondents are moderately aware towards the speed provided the branded broadband service provider, 25.83% of the respondents are not aware and the remaining 12.08% of the respondents are highly aware about the same. (93.33%) of the respondents used their broadband services for their personal and business purposes, followed by majority (92.5%) each of the respondents have stated that they use their broad band services for Email & instant messaging and banking, trading stocks or bill payment purposes respectively. 92.08% of the respondents are using for services like bill

payments, etc., 91.67% of the respondents are using to share music files or photos, 91.25% of the respondents are using as a search engine and purchase of products, 90.42% of the respondents are using for downloading movies to view on PCs, 83.33% of the respondents are using for playing online games and online gambling, 76.67% of the respondents are using for search of information and finally, 53.75% of the respondents are using for downloading movies to view on PCs children learning.

	Highly Important		Mostly Important		Somewhat Important		Fairly Important		Not Important		Total	
	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%
Cost Factor	69	28.75	80	33.33	39	16.25	32	13.33	20	8.33	240	100
Speed	73	30.42	66	27.50	57	23.75	26	10.83	18	7.50	240	100
Installation	71	29.58	57	23.75	71	29.58	22	17.09	0	0.00	240	100
Reliability	84	35.00	50	20.83	74	30.83	20	8.33	12	5.00	240	100
Quality	90	37.50	58	24.17	68	28.33	11	4.58	13	5.42	240	100
Network	107	44.58	56	23.33	55	22.92	7	2.92	15	6.25	240	100
Location	15	6.25	8	3.33	33	13.75	88	36.67	96	40.0	240	100

It is clear from the above table that 33.33% of the respondents considered most important towards the cost factors for using the branded broadband services, while 28.75% of the respondents considered highly important, 16.25% of the respondents opined somewhat important, 13.33% of the respondents considered fairly important and the remaining 8.33% of the respondents stated not important.

It is understood that 30.42% of the respondents considered speed as highly important factor for using branded broadband services, while 27.5% of the respondents opined mostly important, 23.75% of the respondents felt somewhat important, 10.83% of the respondents considered fairly important and the remaining 7.5% of the respondents stated not important.

It is evident that 29.58% of the respondents considered installation as highly important when using the branded broadband services, while 29.58% of the respondents

H₀: Null Hypothesis: There is no significant variance between Frequency of Getting Connected and Satisfaction on branded broadband has excellent uploading & downloading quality

Frequency of Getting Connected and Satisfaction on Branded Broadband Has Excellent Uploading & Downloading Quality:

Frequency of Getting Connected	Satisfaction on branded broadband has excellent uploading & downloading quality					Total
	Highly Satisfied	Satisfied	Neutral	Dissatisfied	Highly Dissatisfied	
Regularly online	12	27	4	7	7	57
Once in a day	18	27	8	14	6	73
Once in a Week	12	26	4	9	2	53
Rarely (not specific)	18	17	8	8	6	57
Total	60	97	24	38	21	240

Source of Variation	SS	d.f.	Mean Square	F-ratio	5% F-limit
Between Columns	988	(5-1) =4	246.88	24.83	F(4,12)= 3.26
Between Rows	47	(4-1) =3	15.73	1.58	F(3,12)= 3.49
Residual of error	119	4 x 3 = 12	9.94		
Total	1154	(5 x 4)-1 = 19			

The table value at 5% level of significance and the calculated F Ratio is 24.83 between columns and 1.58 between rows. The calculated value is more than the table value between columns and the calculated value is less than the table value between rows. Hence, there is significant variance between Frequency of Getting Connected and Satisfaction on branded broadband has excellent uploading & downloading quality

Therefore it is clear that there is significant variance between Frequency of Getting Connected and Satisfaction on branded broadband has excellent uploading & downloading quality.

Findings:

- ✓ Maximum (25.42%) of the respondents have opted BSNL as their service provider for the broadband services
- ✓ As high as 30.42% of the respondents get connected with the broadband once in a day
- ✓ More than half (55%) of the respondents incurred expenses between Rs.500 to 1000 per month
- ✓ Majority (48.75%) of the respondents were aware about the branded broadband services through family
- ✓ Majority (62.08%) of the respondents are highly aware about the Cable Modem of the broadband services. It is clear that most (64.58%) of the respondents are moderately aware about the DSL

broadband services. Maximum (54.17%) of the respondents are moderately aware about fixed wireless broadband services. 42.50% of the respondents are moderately aware about the Satellite internet broadband services.

- ✓ The relationship between Source of Awareness and Awareness about Fixed Wireless Modem Broadband Services is significant. Thus, the null hypothesis is rejected.
- ✓ Suggestions
- ✓ Coimbatore is a well cultured city and more trading is taking place and the business growth seems to be in a high at all times. Even though, the overall corporate segment face recessional periods they strive to grow against these phase and overcome the situation. Thus, indirectly make an impact of Awareness about Broadband services, service providers and types, quality and varieties of services existing in the market.
- ✓ Respondents Hours of Internet Usage is increasing day by day. There is a need to provide customers some discounts and offers on the usage and the timings. This will in turn keep the customer happy and also they will promote through word of mouth.
- ✓ Few of the respondents feel that the billing by service provider is exorbitant and they may intend to change the service provider in future. This information was revealed by the respondents during the survey.

Conclusion:

This information was revealed by the respondents during the survey. The study concludes that when taking the overall survey into consideration the respondents are happy and liked the services provided by their service provider which shall be maintained to keep their customers satisfied to achieve greater heights in the years to come.

References:

1. Cable and telephone companies “version” services by offering different prices for different bandwidths with the same physical plant.
2. Some consumers are able to obtain discounted broadband access by buying two or more services from their cable company. (Black 2001).
3. Large cable multiple system operators (MSOs) such as AT&T and TWC have exclusive contract rights with Excite@Home (now AT&T Broadband Internet service) and Road Runner, respectively, to provide residential broadband services access over their transport facilities.
4. To access an alternative broadband ISP instead of the ISP affiliated with the cable provider, a user of broadband cable access has to pay ‘twice’ (Hausman et al 2001).
5. Always on can increase Internet use. Crandall and Jackson (2001) suggest that when a user has a quick impulse to check the www for data, using a connection that is already established, rather than establishing a dial-up connection, improves the response time by nearly tenfold.